

SOLVING OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS IN THE DESIGN AND PRODUCTION OF DRIVESHAFTS FOR VEHICLES USING COMPUTER MODELLING

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Abstract: The analysis of the stress-strain state of the main assemblies of the cardan shaft of trucks, which determine its resource – the u-joint cross and splined joint, was carried out in the SolidWorks software environment. The bench tests of the cardan shaft showed the adequacy of the developed virtual models of its elements. According to the results of virtual and bench tests, the directions of design, technological and material science solutions for improving the cardan shaft are proposed.

Key words: Transmission, cardan shafts, SolidWorks 2019, CAE, tractors, functional units, cars, Belkard.

Driveshafts in rear- and all-wheel drive vehicle designs are complex dynamic systems consisting of a number of elements made of various types of materials (metal, polymer, composite, etc.) and kinematic connections that allow power to be transferred from the engine to other transmission components. The design of these shafts requires careful consideration of parameters such as torque, speed and rotation angles to ensure efficient power transmission without excessive wear or destruction [1].

For the design and production of cardan shafts at specialized industrial enterprises, computer modelling tools are widely used, which are a powerful tool for optimizing the designs of technical objects, allowing design engineers to

effectively predict their behaviours under various operating conditions [2]. Using simulation software's capabilities allows designers to quickly explore a range of design options, test different scenarios, and fine-tune designed designs before moving on to physical testing. This approach when creating driveshafts used in various types of vehicles and industrial installations helps to save time and financial resources, as well as improve the quality and reliability of both individual elements and the entire design of driveshafts, which makes them an important component in many industrial and automotive applications [3].

The purpose of this work was the design, technological and materials science optimization of vehicle driveshafts using computer modelling tools and finite element analysis methods.

The object of optimization was the design of the cardan transmission 6422-2205010-10 produced, used to equip MAZ-MAN trucks, the model of which is shown in Figure 1.

To build a geometric model of the cardan drive, we used the integrated computer-aided design system SolidWorks 2019, which provides an end-to-end process of design, engineering analysis and preparation for production of products of any complexity and purpose, including the creation of interactive documentation and data exchange with other systems.

The analysis of the stress-strain state of the cardan transmission elements was carried out in the SolidWorks Simulation CAE module, which implements the finite element method [4].

The most important component of the economic potential of the CIS countries and the Republic of Uzbekistan is the machine-building complex, which provides consumers with automotive and tractor equipment that meets modern requirements for material and energy intensity, service life and functional purpose. In the designs of agricultural and automotive equipment (tractors, functional units, cars), railway and urban transport, power plants used in industrial equipment, parts and assemblies made of structural materials of various compositions and

manufacturing technologies are widely used in order to meet technical requirements under conditions of complex influence physical-mechanical, thermal, physical-chemical and other factors. Such units with universal functions, combining parts from various structural materials, include cardan transmissions, which are devices for transmitting and converting drive energy to an actuator or motion system [5-6].

One of the modern industrial enterprises specializing in the production of driveshafts for land vehicles is Belkard OJSC, whose quality system meets the requirements of STB ISO 9001-2015.

Figure 1. 3D model of the cardan transmission of MAZ-MAN trucks.

The most critical elements of the cardan transmission, which determine its technical life, are the hinge unit and the spline connection.

At the first stage of the research, virtual tests were carried out on a model of a driveshaft crosspiece made of 20KhGNTR steel using static (Static) stress analysis according to the Mises criterion (von Mises, forming energy criterion) in the SolidWorks Simulation environment according to the following scheme (Figure 2): 1) constructing the geometry of the object; 2) creation of a mathematical model, including specifying the material and boundary conditions - fastenings and loads; 3) partitioning the model into a finite element mesh; 4) decision. The Mises criterion determines the moment of loss of load-bearing

capacity by comparing the value of the equivalent stress with the yield strength of the material [7-8]. The solved problem (stress data) was displayed on the screen in the form of contour graphs (diagrams), in which the distribution of parameters is encoded in different colors directly on the image of the object (Figure 3, a). Areas with maximum stress (“weak” spots) are indicated in red. The results of virtual tests are presented in the table [9].

Figure 2. Stages of modeling a cross.

a) – geometric model; b) – boundary conditions; v) – finite element mesh

Figure 3. Crosspiece test results.

a) – virtual tests in the SolidWorks Simulation environment; b) – bench tests

Table-1 Results of virtual tests of the crosspiece

№	Parameter	Parameter value	
		minimum	maximum
1.	Tension, MPa	0,2	2,238

2.	Displacement, mm	0	0,9
3.	Equivalent strains	0	$7,69 \cdot 10^{-3}$

To verify the results obtained, bench tests were carried out, during which the values of the destructive torques of the investigated driveshaft parts, as well as the location and nature of these destructions were identified (Figure 3, b). Thus, for the crosspiece, the moment of destruction was $M_{razr} \approx 23500$ N m.

It has been established that in dangerous zones of the cross the tensile strength stresses are exceeded [10].

Analysis of the stress-strain state of the crosspiece and the results of bench tests showed that in the mechanism of formation of the stress-strain state of the crosspiece elements, the processes of frictional interaction of the supports with the needle bearing are of significant importance. Increased values of the friction coefficient, disturbances in the smoothness of micromovements in the interface due to wear and setting phenomena on the actual contact spots lead to an increase in stresses in dangerous sections [11-12]. To optimize the tribological parameters of the “pin – needle bearing” interface, it is proposed to apply a rotaprint coating based on polymer-oligomer mixtures of fluorine-containing components (UPTFE), 5–10 microns thick, or use a grease based on Litol-24, CIATIM-201 lubricants, into which UPTFE particles in an amount of 5–10 wt. %.

Analysis of the bench test results showed the effectiveness of the developed solutions for improving the performance parameters of truck driveshaft crosspieces [11].

As design, technological and materials science solutions to improve the spline joint of the driveshaft of trucks, it is proposed to apply a polyamide-based composite polymer coating to the metal surface of the spline bushing, which provides high parameters of strength, tribotechnical, adhesive and protective characteristics [13-14].

To modify the polyamide, dispersed modifiers and a high-molecular component were used, ensuring compatibility and uniform distribution of

modifying particles throughout the volume of the matrix polymer. As a high-molecular component, it is proposed to introduce a polyamide resin based on aminoamides of rosin acids into the composition of a composite material based on industrial polyamide, which has high thermodynamic compatibility with the matrix component and helps to increase the parameters of its deformation-strength characteristics and hydrophobicity [15]. As functional components of a composite material based on modified polyamides, dispersed particles of carbon-containing components (UDA, colloidal graphite) and metal-containing compounds selected from the group of formic and oxalic acid salts of copper, nickel, zinc and other metals were used.

It has been established that the joint introduction of a polyamide resin based on aminoamides of rosin acids, dispersed particles of carbon-containing components and metal salts provides not only an increase in the homogeneity of functional coatings, but also the achievement of a synergistic effect, which consists in increasing the parameters of operational properties - deformation-strength characteristics and wear resistance, and also resistance to thermal-oxidative environments [16-17].

Thus, based on model concepts that take into account the operating features of cardan transmissions of trucks, using the SolidWorks three-dimensional modeling application package, an assessment analysis of the stress-strain state of the elements of the hinge unit and splined connection was carried out. The basic parameters of the deformation-strength characteristics of composite materials necessary to ensure the effective operation of metal-polymer structures of universal joint drives in real application conditions have been determined. Validation and verification of virtual test results with experimental data indicates the adequacy of the developed models and their full compliance with the actual operating conditions of the cardan drive [18].

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